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11 β -HSD1 inhibitor alleviates non-alcoholic fatty liver disease by activating the AMPK/SIRT1 signaling pathway

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Abstract: We investigated the effect of an 11 β -HSD1 inhibitor (H8) on hepatic steatosis and its mechanism of action. Although H8, a curcumin derivative, has been shown to alleviate insulin resistance, its effect on non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) remains unknown. Rats were fed a high-fat diet (HFD) for 8 weeks, intraperitoneally injection with streptozotocin (STZ) to induce NAFLD, then treated with H8 (3 or 6 mg/kg/d) or curcumin (6 mg/kg/d) for 4 weeks to evaluate the effects of H8 on NAFLD. H8 significantly alleviated HFD+STZ-induced lipid accumulation, fibrosis, and inflammation and improved liver function. 11 β -HSD1 overexpression was established by transfecting animals and HepG2 cells with lentivirus carrying the 11 β -HSD1 gene to confirm that H8 improved NAFLD by reducing 11 β -HSD1. An AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) inhibitor (Compound C, 10 μ M for 2 h) was used to confirm that H8 increased AMPK by inhibiting 11 β -HSD1, thereby restoring lipid metabolic homeostasis. A silencing-related enzyme 1 (SIRT1) inhibitor (EX572, 10 μ M for 4 h) and a SIRT1 activator (SRT1720, 1 μ M for 4 h) were used to confirm that H8 exerted anti-inflammatory effects by elevating SIRT1 expression. Our findings demonstrate that H8 alleviates hepatic steatosis by inhibiting 11 β -HSD1, activating the AMPK/SIRT1 signaling pathway.

Keywords: 11-beta-Hydroxysteroid Dehydrogenase Type 1 (11 β -HSD1); Curcumin; Non-alcoholic Fatty Liver Disease (NAFLD); Lipid Metabolism; Anti-inflammatory

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Supplementary Figure 1. Relative cell viability of FFAs after 24h treatment.

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Supplementary Figure 2. Transfection efficiency

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Supplementary Figure 3. AMPK and SIRT1 protein expression levels in HepG2 cells

Supplementary Figure 4. Body weight change

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Supplementary Figure 5. Grayscale values of Oil Red O in rat liver.

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Supplementary Figure 6. Relative cell viability after H8 treatment.

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Supplemental Table 1. The primer sequences used in qPCR.

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Gene	Forward	Reverse
GAPDH (rat)	TGTGAAGCTCATTTTCCTGGTAT	GATGGGGACTCCTCAGCAAC
GAPDH (human)	CACCATCTTCCAGGAGCGAG	TGATGACCCTTTTGGCTCCC
β-Actin (mouse)	CCTAGGCACCAGGGTGTGAT	AGCACAGGGTGCTCCTCA
SIRT1 (mouse)	TCGGCTACCGAGGTCCATA	CCGCAAGGCGAGCATAGATA
SIRT1 (rat)	TGGAAGGAAAGCAATTTTGAAATA	CTGCAACCTGCTCCAAGGTA
SIRT1 (human)	CATTCCTCAAGTTTGCAAAGGAAAT	CGAAGTAGTTTTTCCTTCCTTATCTG
HSD1-11β (mouse)	ACTCAGACCTCGCTGTCTCT	TGGGTCATTTTCCCAGCCAA
HSD1-11β (rat)	CTCCTCCATGGCTGGGAAAA	GAAGCCGAGGACACAGAGAG
SREBP1 (rat)	TCTTGACCGACATCGAAGACAT	GCCTGTGTCTCCTGTCTCAC
SREBP1 (human)	CTGACCGACATCGAAGGTGA	CCAGCATAGGGTGGGTCAAA
HSL (rat)	GTCAAACCCTCCAGAGCCAA	GTGAGAATGCCGAGGCTGTA
HSL (human)	CCTCGTCCTCACTCCTCCC	TTAAGTAAGGCACAGCCCGC
FAS (rat)	TGTACCCTCTAGCTGGACCC	CCAGGCTAAGGGCAATGGAA
FAS (human)	TCGTGTTGACTTCTCGCTCC	CCATCTCTCAAGACCACGGC
TNF-α (rat)	ATGGGCTCCCTCTCATCAGT	GCTTGGTGGTTTGCTACGAC
TNF-α (human)	TCTCCTTCTGATCGTGGA	CAGCTTGAGGGTTTGCTACAAC
PGC-1α (rat)	TGGAGTGACATAGAGTGTGCTG	TATGTTTCGCGGGCTCATTGT
PGC-1α (human)	TCTGACCCCAGAGTCACCAA	GTGGAGTTAGGCCTGCAGTT
PPAR-γ (rat)	GCTTGTGAAGGATGCAAGGG	GCCCAAACCTGATGGCATTG
PPAR-γ (human)	GCAATCAAAGTGGAGCCTGC	TCTCCGGAAGAAACCCTTGC

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Supplemental Table 2. The primary antibodies used in WB.

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Gene	Forward	Reverse
β-actin	Cell Signaling Technology	1:1000
SIRT1	Affinity	1:1000

11 β -HSD1	Abcam	1:1000
AMPK- α 1	Abcam	1:1000
p-AMPK- α 1	Abcam	1:1000
sterol regulatory element binding protein 1 (SREBP1)	Abcam	1:1000
fatty acid synthase (FASN)	Affinity	1:1000
carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1 β (CPT-1 β)	Abcam	1:1000
acetyl coenzyme A carboxylase (ACC1)	Abcam	1:1000
p-ACC1	Cell Signaling Technology	1:1000
hormone-sensitive triglyceride lipase (HSL)	Abcam	1:1000
interleukin-6 (IL-6)	Abcam	1:500
interleukin-17 (IL-17)	Abcam	1:1000
tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α)	Bioss	1:500
peroxisome proliferator-activator receptor gamma (PPAR- γ)	Affinity	1:1000
peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1- α (PGC-1 α)	Affinity	1:1000
nuclear factor kappa-B p65 (NF-kB p65)	Abcam	1:1000
NF- κ B-p-p65	Affinity	1:1000
